

Activity profiles during wheelchair tennis: Effects of division, result and score margin

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Abstract The purpose of this study was to compare the activity profiles of elite wheelchair tennis (WT) players during match-play for men, women and quad divisions and to explore how result and score margin affect these profiles. Activity profiles of seventeen of the top 8 ranked WT players from the men's (n = 7), women's (n = 6) and quad (n = 4) divisions were monitored during the NEC Wheelchair Tennis Masters 2017 using a radio frequency-based indoor tracking system (ITS) and inertial measurement units (IMU). Data were collected from 22 matches, resulting in 73 individual sets of data. Data were analysed with regards to the result of each set (win/loss) and margin of the result (small ≤ 3 ; large > 3 games differential). Distance, mean and peak speed and the time spent in fixed speed zones were analysed by the ITS. Acceleration, rotational velocity and rotational acceleration and direction of turns were quantified by the IMU. Activity profiles were elevated during men's matches compared to both women's and quads and for women's matches compared to quads for most parameters. Few differences in activity profiles were observed between winning and losing sets. Alternatively, independent of result, distances covered, peak speed, time spent and number of high-speed activity (HSA) performed were significantly greater during sets with small score margins ($p \leq 0.035$). Significant interactions between result and score margin were also observed for a number of parameters. Trivial to small differences (effect sizes [ES] ≤ 0.3) in mean speed, time spent and number of HSA performed were revealed when losing, regardless of margin, whereas large increases (ES ≥ 1.3) were revealed when winning by a small compared to large margin. In conclusion, activity profiles differ according to division and are typically elevated during sets with a small score margin in WT players, which should be taken into consideration by coaches and practitioners when monitoring and planning players physical training loads.

Keywords External load, internal load, wheelchair tennis, classification

Introduction

Wheelchair tennis (WT) is a court-based wheelchair sport that has been included at the Paralympic Games since 1992. Athletes with a lower limb impairment are eligible to compete in the 'open' category, of which a separate division exists for both men and women. Athletes with a lower and upper limb impairment compete in a quad division, where men and women compete together [1]. Previous research into the physical demands of WT has revealed that players typically cover distances of 2816 ± 844 m at a mean speed of 0.7 ± 0.2 m/s and reach peak speeds of 3.4 ± 0.4 m/s [2]. However, little is known about how these demands differ between athletes from different divisions and also how situational factors such as result and winning margin can further affect these demands. To optimize the physical preparation of WT players, an

understanding of these factors is clearly warranted. Thus, the aims of the current study were to firstly establish the physical demands of elite WT players during competition and to examine how these demands differ across the different divisions (men's, women's & quads). A secondary aim was to determine the impact of result and score margin on these parameters.

Methods

Physical performance data were collected from 17 international WT players (age = 30 ± 8 yrs) during the NEC Wheelchair Tennis Masters 2017. This competition includes the top 8 ranked players in the world for the men's ($n = 7$) and women's ($n = 6$) divisions and top 6 for the quad ($n = 4$) division and is played on indoor hard courts.

During matches, activity profiles were measured using a radio-frequency, indoor tracking system (ITS) (Ubisense, Cambridge, U.K) sampling at ~ 16 Hz and three inertial measurement units (IMU) (Shimmer3, Shimmer Sensing, Ireland) sampling at ~ 200 Hz. Players were asked to report an overall rating of perceived exertion (RPE) for each set using the CR-10 scale within 30 minutes after the match. This was then multiplied by the set duration to give a session RPE (sRPE) value and a measure of internal load.

A total of 22 matches were collected, resulting in 73 individual sets of data. All data were analysed with regards to i) the result of each set (win/loss) and ii) the margin of the result (small ≤ 3 ; large > 3 games differential).

Results

Differences in physical and technical performance between divisions are demonstrated in Table 1. Activity profiles were higher during Men's matches in relation to both Women's and Quad's matches and during Women's matches in relation to Quad's matches for most parameters. Session RPE was the only parameter not to differ significantly between divisions.

Few differences in activity profiles were observed during winning and losing sets of WT. Significantly more time and a higher relative number of high-speed activities (HAS) were performed during losing sets, yet the effect sizes (ES) of these differences were small and the 95% CI spanned zero. The only interaction between division and result was identified for the peak speed reached. Differences in peak speeds during winning and losing sets were trivial for Men (3.85 ± 0.37 vs. 3.83 ± 0.26 m·s⁻¹, ES = 0.1). Whereas small decreases in peak speed were revealed for Women (3.32 ± 0.27 vs. 3.44 ± 0.24 m·s⁻¹, ES = 0.5) and moderate increases in peak speed were observed for Quad's (3.32 ± 0.34 vs. 3.02 ± 0.16 m·s⁻¹, ES = 1.1) during losing sets compared to winning sets.

Score margin had a significant effect on many performance measures analysed during WT, with moderate to large increases in activity profiles observed during sets with small score margins. The only interaction between score margin and division was for the time spent performing HSA, whereby moderate increases in HSA were revealed during sets with small score margins for Men's (15.3 ± 3.8 vs. $11.7 \pm 4.5\%$, ES = 0.9) and Quad's (5.4 ± 0.3 vs. $4.5 \pm 1.5\%$, ES = 0.7), whereas only small increases were revealed during Women's (7.8 ± 1.8 vs. $7.4 \pm 1.5\%$, ES = 0.2) in relation to large score margins.

Activity profiles of elite wheelchair tennis players

Table 1. Physical demands of WT across different divisions. Values are means \pm SD and are presented per set. Low, moderate and high-speed activities are referred to as LSA, MSA and HAS respectively. R and NR refer to the direction of turns being performed (R in the direction of the racket hand; NR in the direction of the non-racket hand).

	Main effect (division)	Men's (n = 27)	Women's (n = 24)	Quad's (n = 14)
Duration (mm:ss)	0.016	39:18 (12:22)	34:01 (10:43)	28:50 (08:07)
Distance (m)	0.005	2220 (802)	1841 (648)	1275 (347)
Mean speed (m·s ⁻¹)	<0.0005	1.20 (0.12)	1.10 (0.09)	1.01 (0.08)
Peak speed (m·s ⁻¹)	<0.0005	3.84 (0.31)	3.39 (0.25)	3.17 (0.30)
LSA (%)	0.002	44.3 (6.5)	44.4 (7.0)	53.3 (5.8)
MSA (%)	0.005	41.7 (4.9)	48.0 (7.4)	42.0 (5.2)
HSA (%)	<0.0005	14.1 (4.3)	7.6 (1.7)	4.8 (1.3)
No. HSA (n·min ⁻¹)	<0.0005	3.5 (0.7)	2.5 (0.7)	1.7 (0.4)
Mean acceleration (m·s ⁻²)	<0.0005	1.08 (0.18)	0.91 (0.15)	0.72 (0.08)
Turns – R (n·min ⁻¹)	<0.0005	5.6 (0.5)	6.2 (1.1)	4.9 (0.8)
Turns – NR (n·min ⁻¹)	0.016	7.5 (0.7)	7.2 (1.0)	6.8 (0.6)
Rotational velocity (deg·s ⁻¹)	<0.0005	72.1 (5.0)	82.4 (8.9)	63.7 (4.9)
Rotational acceleration (deg·s ⁻²)	<0.0005	205 (28)	211 (29)	144 (31)
Session RPE (au)	0.175	136 (68)	101 (76)	94 (32)

Conclusion

The activity profiles of elite WT players differ considerably according to the division they compete in. Although profiles were comparable across winning and losing sets, small score margins elevated the workload of players. These findings should be acknowledged by coaches and practitioners and could be implemented to optimize players physical training loads specific to the demands of competition.

References

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